

An In Vitro Investigation on the Impact of Curqfen® and Curcumin on Ibotenic Acid Induced Memory Impairment

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ABSTRACT

Herbal drugs are widely used for treatment of many disease including Neuro-Degenerative (ND) diseases like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other memory related disease. CurQfen® (CF) is a unique product from the Akay Flavours and Aromatics Pvt. Ltd, Cochin, Kerala, CF is an enhanced bioavailable form of Curcumin. In the present study an attempt is made to investigate the possible protective effect of CF using Ibotenic acid (IBO) induced dementia and brain-lesions. Male Wistar albino rats were treated p.o with CF (200 and 400mg/kg), Curcumin (CC) 400mg/kg daily for 14 days. Ibotenic acids (IBO 5µg/µl, ICV) were used to induce memory impairment. The neurotransmitter levels were assessed by UV spectrophotometrically. The study showed that IBO significantly increased (P<0.001) the brain levels of acetyl cholinesterase, nitrite and malondialdehyde while CF and CC restored it. The working memory and learning memory errors were enhanced following IBO treatment, while CF and CC significantly reduced them. It is concluded that treatment with CF offers a protection against IBO induced dementia and brain-lesions, as evidenced by the brain levels of neurotransmitters.

Keywords: CurQfen®, Wistar albino rats, Ibotenic acid, Curcumin, malondialdehyde, acetyl cholinesterase.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal drugs are widely used for treatment of many disease including Neuro-Degenerative (ND) diseases like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other memory related disease. Herbal medicine offers several options to modify the progress and symptoms of AD.^[1]

Curcumin (CC), a major component extracted from the rhizome *Curcuma longa*, has been consumed by humans as a curry spice for centuries. It has been extensively studied for its wide range of biological activities, including anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, anti-infection and antitumor properties, but bioavailability is a problem. The reasons for the reduced bioavailability are low intrinsic activity, poor

absorption, high rate of metabolism, inactivity of metabolic products and/or rapid elimination, clearance from the body, low plasma and tissue levels of CC appear to be due to poor absorption, rapid metabolism and rapid systemic elimination. As many as 95% of CC products on the market are not well absorbed by the body and instead pass through the GI tract. CC exhibits relatively poor oral bioavailability and a short serum half-life (< 45 minutes), which could contribute to its limited therapeutic window in head trauma.^[2]

CurQfen® (CF) is an enhanced bioavailable form of CC and a unique formulation of curcuminoids from turmeric along with galactomannans from fenugreek to enhance bioavailability and 20 times more absorption in in vivo and 15.8 times the

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bioavailability in human studies than standard curcuminoids and prolonged half-life in blood plasma. Controlled release of CurQfen® Curcumin/Fenugreek complex employs a unique composition of non-digestible, fermentable galactomannan-protein matrix from fenugreek to enhance the bioavailability of active curcuminoids. CF possesses the optimum hydrophobic-hydrophilic balance for the colloidal dispersion of CC upon swelling in the intestinal fluid. [3]

ND diseases occur when neurons in the brain and spinal cord begin to deteriorate. The major ND diseases includes Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Prion disease, Motor neurone diseases (MND), Huntington's disease (HD), Spino-cerebellar ataxia (SCA) and Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA)⁴. Reasons for developing ND disease

is oxidative stress in the aging brain. Along with this, excessive or persistent activation of glutamate gated ion channels may also contribute to the same and mutations in the β -amyloid ($A\beta$) precursor protein, causing Alzheimer disease (AD); α -synuclein, causing Parkinson's disease (PD); or micro tubule-associated protein tau, causing Fronto-temporal dementia (FTD) with Parkinsonism. [5,6,8,9]

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive and irreversible debilitating form of dementia. It is characterized by progressive memory impairment and diminished cognitive performance. [7]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal used

36 young male Wistar rats were procured from the animal house of Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, MG University, Cheruvandoor. Rats weighing 150-250g at the beginning of the experiment were housed five per cage respectively at 12:12 h light/dark cycle and fed ad libitum. The animals were divided into different groups and were kept for acclimatization. They were maintained in uniform climatic conditions.

Materials used

Table 1: List of chemicals and reagents used

No.	Chemicals & Reagents	Supplier
1.	Curcumin	Akay Flavours and Aromatics Pvt.Ltd, Cochin, Kerala, India.
2.	CurQfen®	Akay Flavours and Aromatics Pvt.Ltd, Cochin, Kerala, India.
3.	Ibotenic acid	Cayman chemical company, Michigan
4.	0.1M Phosphate buffer	Sigma Aldrich
5.	DTNB Reagent	Sigma Aldrich
6.	Acetylthiocholine	Sigma Aldrich
7.	Sodium dodecyl sulphate	Sigma Aldrich
8.	Acetic acid	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd.
9.	Thiobarbituric acid	Alpha Chemika
10.	Butanol	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd.
11.	Ninhydrin reagent	Sigma Aldrich

Acute toxicity studies

Acute toxicity studies for CurQfen® were already conducted by Sunny et al., 2014. It was found to be safe up to 2000 mg/kg body weight by oral route.

Preparation of ibotenic acid

It was prepared by dissolving in the distilled water and stored at deep freezing temperature.

Test drugs:

Curcumin (CC) and CurQfen® (CF) were weighed and uniformly distributed in sunflower oil (SFO) by stirring.

Standard drug:

Donepezil 5 mg tablets were powdered, weighed and uniformly distributed in SFO.

Surgical Procedure

All the animals were kept on overnight fasting on the day prior to surgery. All the equipment used during the surgical procedure was sterilised by washing with ethanol (90%) before every use. The rats were administered with Oxytetracyclin inj. intramuscularly (IM) 1 h prior to the surgery to prevent infection. The rats were anesthetized intraperitoneally (i.p) with Ketamine (100 mg/kg) and Xylazine (10 mg/kg). The rats were kept in supine position on a surgical board and a cotton ball was placed under the lower jaw to prevent any obstruction to air flow during the surgery. The hair was removed from the head using scissors and the surgical area was wiped with cotton dipped in alcohol and later with betadine solution. A midline sagittal incision was made in the scalp using a scalpel blade. The excess blood was removed with cotton and cleaned with normal saline (NS). The co-ordinates for drilling holes were identified using a stainless steel scale. Holes were drilled in the skull over the lateral ventricles on one of the hemispheres using the following coordinates: **0.8mm posterior to bregma; 1.5mm lateral to the sagittal suture.** All injections were made using a 10- μ l Hamilton syringe. The needle of the micro-syringe was put **3.8mm beneath the surface of the brain.** All the groups except the

Control received 5 μ l of IBO in lateral ventricle. Control group received bi-distilled water (5 μ l) instead of IBO. The syringe was kept in the position for 30 s after the injection to avoid the leakage of IBO by capillary action. A piece of absorbable soft gelatine sponge was kept inside the incision to prevent the excessive blood loss. The incision was sutured and betadine ointment was applied over the wound. The animals were caged individually and transferred to the post-surgical recovery room. [10,11,12]

Post-Surgical Care

Oxytetracycline and Pentazocine injection were given once daily IM and SC respectively, for the next three days. The hind and fore limbs of the animals were cleaned with ethanol (90%) every 12 h to prevent any faecal contamination of wound and the bedding was changed every day. Food and water was supplied after 24 h of surgery. Betadine ointment was applied every 12 h for the next two days to prevent any chances of infection and faster wound healing. [13,14]

Fig 1: Post-surgical care

General Procedure

After the acclimatization period, the rats were divided into 6 different groups each containing 6 animals. The rats received bilateral I.C.V injection of a water solution of IBO except for the control group. The Control group received bi-distilled water instead of IBO as I.C.V injection. Donepezil (DPL) was used as the standard drug. DPL, CC and CF were administered orally to specific groups after two days of surgery for the next 15 days. Control group received SFO p.o. After a recovery period of 14 days from the day of surgery, the hippocampal AchE,

nitrite level, lipid peroxidation and glutamate from isolated brain tissues were estimated.^[15,16]

In vitro Methods

1. Estimation Acetyl cholinesterase

The rat were decapitated; brains are removed quickly and placed in ice cold saline. Frontal cortex, hippocampus and septum are quickly dissected out on a Petri dish chilled on crushed ice. The tissues are weighed and homogenized in 0.1M Phosphate buffer (pH 8). 0.4ml aliquot of the homogenate is added to a cuvette containing 2.6 ml phosphate buffer (0.1M, pH 8) and 100µl of DTNB. The contents of the cuvette are mixed thoroughly by bubbling air and absorbance is measured at 412 nm in a spectrophotometer. When absorbance reaches a stable value, it is recorded as the basal reading. 20µl of substrate i.e., acetylthiocholine is added and change in absorbance is recorded. Change in the absorbance per minute is thus determined.^[17]

2. Estimation of Nitrite level in rat brain

To 0.5 mL of cell lysate, 0.1 mL of sulphosalicylic acid was added and vortexed well for 30 minutes. The samples were then centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 15 min. The protein-free supernatant was used for the estimation of nitrite levels. To 200 µL of the supernatant, 30 µL of 10% NaOH was added, followed by 300 µL of Tris-HCl buffer and mixed

well. To this, 530 µL of Griess reagent was added and incubated in the dark for 10–15 min, and the absorbance was read at 540 nm against a Griess reagent blank. Sodium nitrite solution was used as the standard. The amount of nitrite present in the samples was estimated from the standard curves obtained.^[18]

3. Estimation of Lipid peroxidase (LPO)

The animals were sacrificed, whole brains was removed quickly and placed in ice-cold saline. The tissues were weighed and homogenized in 0.1M Phosphate buffer (pH 8) at 2400rpm. 0.2ml of the supernatant from brain homogenate 0.2 ml of SDS, 1.5 ml of acetic acid and 1.5 ml of TBA were added. The mixture was made up to 4 ml with water and then heated in a water bath at 95°C for 60 minutes. After cooling, 1 ml of water and 5 ml of n-butanol / pyridine mixture were added and shaken vigorously. After centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes, the organic layer was taken and its absorbance was read at 532 nm. The level of lipid peroxides was expressed as micro moles of MDA released/ g wet tissue.^[19]

RESULTS

Estimation of Acetyl cholinesterase

Acetyl cholinesterase concentration was increased in IBO group while CF and CC was found to be reduced. Here the result shows that there was a significant reduction in acetyl cholinesterase level in test groups.

Table 2: Amount of AchE level after treatment with DPL, CC, CF and IBO was given below

Groups	Control	IBO	DPL	CC	CF(L)	CF(H)
AchE in µmol/min /mg of tissue	0.5133±0.018	0.8667±0.020	0.6333±0.015*	0.7333±0.009*	0.7000±0.006*	0.6800±0.005**

Fig: 2 Amount of Acetyl cholinesterase

Estimation of Nitrite

Nitrite concentration were increased in IBO group while CF and CC was found to be reduced. Here the result shows that there was a significant reduction in nitrite level in test groups.

Table: 3 Amount of nitrite level after treatment with DPL, CC, CF and IBO was given below.

Groups	Control	IBO	DPL	CC	CF(L)	CF(H)
Amount of nitrite in μg /ml of cell lysate	8.433 \pm 0.120	15.43 \pm 0.145	9.500 \pm 0.115**	12.40 \pm 0.173**	11.40 \pm 0.152**	10.23 \pm 0.067**

Fig: 3 Amount of nitrite level

Estimation of Malondialdehyde

Malondialdehyde concentration were increased in IBO group while CF and CC was found to be reduced.

Here the result shows that there was a significant reduction in malondialdehyde level in CF group

Table: 4 Amount of MDA level after treatment with DPL, CC, CF and IBO was given below.

Groups	Control	IBO	DPL	CC	CF(L)	CF(H)
Amount of MDA in $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ of tissue	1.533 \pm 0.033	3.533 \pm 0.120	1.933 \pm 0.088***	2.900 \pm 0.115*	2.567 \pm 0.145**	2.067 \pm 0.088**

Fig: 4 Amount of malondialdehyde level

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that, CurQfen® offers greater protection against IBO induced dementia and brain-lesions. CF has significant nootropic activity and found to be more effective than plain Curcumin as evidenced by the in vitro estimations.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

No conflicts of interest regarding this article.

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